

THE ROLE OF PATRIOTIC IDEAS AND WORKS IN OUR LEGISLATION IN THE WORKS OF GAFUR GULAM

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ABSTRACT

This article expresses the fact that the history of the Uzbek people has found its artistic embodiment in the poetry and prose of Gafur Gulam, and through the content of short stories, epics, stories about the writer's colorful creativity, patriotic ideas of the creator, conveyed his views on the path of the people's benefit to readers. It is also noted that the role of the works of the Great Creator in the issue of national laws by the competent authorities is immeasurable.

The great writer of Uzbek literature of the 20th century Gafur Gulam was born on May 10, 1903 in the Shayhontohur street of Tashken in a peasant family. His father was literate. Gafur Gulam, who was orphaned by his father at the age of nine and his mother at the age of fifteen, first studied at the old school, and then at the Russian school. The autobiographical story "Shum bola" (1936) clearly describes the childhood of the creator, besides The Life of Tashkent at the beginning of the century.

The history of the Uzbek people has found its artistic embodiment in the poetry and prose of Gafur Gulam. The writer's work was composed of colorful poems, epics, odes, stories and short stories. Especially the work of the writer after the war acquired a large place in the development of Uzbek literature.

Our great creator was not limited only to his work, but also engaged in translation, through which he expanded his worldview, shared with readers the news that he learned from foreign literature.

As an example, we can show skillful translations of the works of Pushkin, Lermontov, Mayakovsky, Nazim Hikmat, Rustaveli, Shakespeare, Dante, Bomarshe and others.

Describing Gafur Gulam as a patriotic writer, let us dwell one after another on the valuable work of the writer. After all, through the content of the works, it is expressed how patriotic our writer.

The story "Netay" is rich in broad social generalizations and attracts the reader with its fact that it is based on real events. Through this short story, it can be noticed that the writer is able to skillfully use the techniques of his work, research, prose. That is, the last Bukhara Emir stays in Tashkent on a trip to Petersburg to please the Emir, while the rich were ready for anything and bring a girl named Netay. The writer pleasantly expresses the image of ordinary

workers in the buyer. Seeds and their women feed a girl named Netay, who, despite the difficulties of life...

A topical work of his time was the saga "Yo'ldosh", which spoke of a powerful force in the upbringing of the younger generation. In the civil war, loved ones lose satellites. Like other orphans, neglected children, this boy is taken care of by the state — they create boarding houses and orphanages for him, which are shelters.

Orphanage educators are always ready for the protection of their homeland's independence. In the epic, with great skill and warmth, the Comrade's meeting with his father is reflected, the figure of people who fulfill their debt is deeply and widely revealed. The theme of the defender of the fatherland was further developed and deepened in the further work of Gafur Gulam in 1941 - 1945. He encourages people to focus on "Have patience, have talent" on victory over the Nazis. The poet glorifies the place of the Uzbek woman in the economic development of the country in the post-war periods.

In the epic "Ikki akt", he praises the resettlement of villages, expresses the feelings of Uzbek farming and their future dream. The epic is strong in its true commitment to the truth of life. A historically reliable picture of Uzbek farming is drawn here. This topic also sounds in the epic "Kokand". In his time, he was popular in the people and acted as a propaganda in the struggle to strengthen agriculture.

Gafur Gulam is also known as a master of short, sharp-plot stories, and instead of a narrative style, he uses it in the form of a lively friendly discussion filled with questions and answers from the writer, through author's speech and a free face to the reader. Many prose works created by Ghafur Gulam in the 30s are devoted to new human relations. The main problems and solutions that he covered in his works are the moral education of a person, the struggle for his spiritual and cultural development. The author creates bright positive emblems in his prose works. Having become the owner of a big heart in the story "memory", the positive hero Zhora brings up a child of a stranger. It was through the attitude of an ordinary person to an alien child that the author showed the high moral level of the Zhora.

As we read the works of the writer, we can also find solutions to the current social problems. Among the works of the writer as a solution to the social problems, offenses observed in the society, one can understand education and upbringing as a major factor. Of course, from the legal side, we also look at the pursuit of an end to each one with the norm of law in order to prevent all offenses is not suitable, otherwise it will cause legal idealism, which will cause a distorted form of law.

Gafur Gulam devoted many of his works to children. The story "Shum bola" is considered relatively lucky. The hero himself talks about his tragic life. The boy runs away from his house looking at his aunt because of his mother's punishment while taking the products out of his house. But here, the child is not lucky: he accidentally kills his uncle's quail and leaves this house too. Thus, he begins to wander and wander. The writer focuses his attention on describing the worries and inner experiences of the shum child. The depiction of external events, objects and all that surrounds the little hero serves in a deep manifestation of human feelings. It is all subject to this — the point of view of the statement of the event, the landscape and the embodiment of the work.

By reading this work, a person will understand how little he says thanks. In the current time in which we live, young people are only required to make the most of their attention and opportunities. It is also enough to give an example of a normative legal document developed by our state that the fate of each younger generation is important for the future of the nation and the development of the motherland. It is important to say that the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on 14.09.2016 by the LRU 406, was also included on the side of the president as a goal to develop a juvenile code on the rights of the child in one of the 100 goals in the strategy of actions for 2022-2026. Because we can learn foreign experience and gain access to the successful side of them, but it is not advisable to make a transplant totally. Because each nation also has its own mentality and traditions of its people. To the future generation, it is necessary to create opportunities based on the environment in which they are being brought up. And when carrying out such responsible work, we need to look back, understand the mistakes and shortcomings and correct them. And the works that clearly show the original internal experiences of manashun-like bolalr, his problems in upbringing, are the most kata auxiliary factor. Because the perfect elaboration of laws requires not only legal knowledge, but also attention to all aspects that concern children, young people.

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